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ABSTRACT

¹H spin-lattice Nuclear Magnetic Resonance relaxometry experiments have been performed for collagen and collagen-based artificial tissues in the frequency range of 10 kHz–20 MHz. The studies were performed for non-hydrated and hydrated materials. The relaxation data have been interpreted as including relaxation contributions originating from ¹H–¹H and ¹H–¹⁴N dipole–dipole interactions, the latter leading to Quadrupole Relaxation Enhancement effects. The ¹H–¹H relaxation contributions have been decomposed into terms associated with dynamical processes on different time scales. A comparison of the parameters for the non-hydrated and hydrated systems has shown that hydration leads to a decrease in the dipolar relaxation constants without significantly affecting the dynamical processes. In the next step, the relaxation data for the hydrated systems were interpreted in terms of a model assuming two-dimensional translational diffusion of water molecules in the vicinity of the macromolecular surfaces and a sub-diffusive motion leading to a power law of the frequency dependencies of the relaxation rates. It was found that the water diffusion process is slowed down by at least two orders of magnitude compared to bulk water diffusion. The frequency dependencies of the relaxation rates in hydrated tissues and hydrated collagen are characterized by different power laws ($\omega_H^{-\beta}$, where ω_H denotes the ¹H resonance frequency): the first of about 0.4 and the second close to unity.

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I. INTRODUCTION

People suffer from severe injuries, congenital defects, and chronic wounds that are difficult to regenerate. Tissue engineering plays a vital role in regenerative medicine. The process of producing artificial tissue involves several steps, such as the isolation and cultivation of cells and the insertion of them into scaffolds.^{1–4} Tissue regeneration requires increasing the number of cells in the tissue and building up an extracellular matrix composed of water and fibrous

structural proteins such as collagen, elastin, fibronectin, vitronectin, and polysaccharides.^{1,2} Acellular dermal matrices utilize the qualities of the native extracellular matrix to enhance the regeneration of the patient's own tissue.⁵ Artificial dermal matrices are used not only as a covering for soft tissue wounds but are also extensively exploited in reconstructive surgeries.^{6–8} Commercially available dermal matrices are obtained from both human and animal species (bovine and porcine) and various tissue sources, such as the dermis, pericardium, and intestinal mucosa.^{9,10}

In this work, the potential of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) relaxometry has been exploited to inquire into the dynamical properties of artificial dermal tissues based on collagen compared to collagen itself. The comparison has been performed for non-hydrated and hydrated systems. The dynamics of water molecules in the macromolecular matrix is one of the key factors determining the application properties of artificial biomaterials and, consequently, the therapeutic outcome. NMR relaxation studies are a highly appreciated source of information about the dynamical and structural properties of advanced materials. Classical NMR relaxation experiments are performed at a single, high magnetic field (resonance frequency). Applying high magnetic fields is undoubtedly of great benefit from the perspective of medical diagnostics (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) and investigating molecular structure (high resolution NMR spectroscopy). However, when it comes to NMR relaxation studies, exploiting only high magnetic fields leads to serious limitations. According to spin relaxation theory,^{11–13} the most efficient relaxation mechanism at a given frequency is associated with dynamical processes occurring on a time scale matching the reciprocal frequency. Although this is a simplified statement, not taking into account several other conditions, it reflects the fact that at high magnetic fields, one mostly probes fast dynamical processes. Fast field cycling technology enables performing relaxation experiments over a broad range of magnetic fields, encompassing more than three orders of magnitude, from about 10 kHz to 20 MHz (referring to ¹H resonance frequency). In this way, one can probe dynamical processes occurring on different time scales in a single experiment. In addition to that, the shape of the frequency dependence of the spin-lattice relaxation rate makes it possible to identify the mechanism of the molecular motion—in other words, one can distinguish between different kinds of dynamics, such as rotational and translational diffusion or polymer specific motion.^{14–16} One can also get insight into geometrical restrictions (anisotropy of the motion)—for instance, one can distinguish between isotropic (three dimensional) and anisotropic (two dimensional) translation diffusion.^{17–20} This is possible because of the different mathematical forms of time correlation functions associated with different mechanisms of molecular motion.^{21–25} Relaxation rates are given as linear combinations of spectral density functions, which are Fourier transforms of the time correlation functions. As the forms of the spectral density functions are motion specific, the shapes of the frequency dependencies of the relaxation rates reflect the mechanism of the motion.

This unique potential of NMR relaxometry has been exploited for molecular and ionic systems of different complexity,^{26–29} including protein systems. Before discussing specific models of motion developed for protein systems, one should consider the quantum-mechanical framework of the relaxation processes. As hydrated proteins are heterogeneous systems including different pools of hydrogen atoms (such as hydrogen atoms of water molecules and of protein molecules—they can undergo exchange dynamics with the water pool), the relaxation process has been described by a set of two equations, including cross relaxation terms.^{30–32} As far as frequency dependent NMR relaxation studies of biological (heterogeneous) systems are concerned, experimentally observed power laws have been attributed to the dynamics of the macromolecular backbones.^{33–39} The power law typically ranges between 0.5 and 0.8.^{39–41} Lorentzian form spectral density functions characteristic of the rotation

dynamics of proteins in solutions change to a power law as a result of cross-linking leading to immobilization of the macromolecules.^{39,42} The dynamical scenario has been complemented by the concept of water diffusion on the macromolecular surfaces.^{40,43–46} Eventually, we wish to stress the concept of decomposing the frequency dependencies of the relaxation rates into components expressed in terms of Lorentzian spectral densities, proposed for parameterizing the dynamical processes by providing insight into a distribution of the correlation times.^{47,48}

The goal of this work is twofold. The first is to reveal the dynamical properties of collagen based biomaterials, using as an example two kinds of artificial tissues (skin). The second is to demonstrate the potential of NMR relaxometry to disclose the dynamics of different molecular fractions in complex systems.

II. THEORY

¹H relaxation processes in biological systems originate primarily from ¹H–¹H and ¹H–¹⁴N magnetic dipole–dipole interactions. This implies that the overall ¹H spin-lattice relaxation rate, $R_1(\omega_H)$ (where ω_H denotes the ¹H resonance frequency in angular frequency units) is given as

$$R_1(\omega_H) = R_1^{HH}(\omega_H) + R_1^{HN}(\omega_H), \quad (1)$$

where $R_1^{HH}(\omega_H)$ and $R_1^{HN}(\omega_H)$ denote the relaxation contributions associated with the ¹H–¹H and ¹H–¹⁴N dipole–dipole interactions. The $R_1^{HH}(\omega_H)$ relaxation contribution can be expressed as^{11–13}

$$R_1^{HH}(\omega_H) = C^{HH} [J(\omega_H) + 4J(2\omega_H)], \quad (2)$$

where the quantity $J(\omega)$ denotes a spectral density function—the Fourier transform of the corresponding time correlation function characterizing the molecular motion leading to fluctuations of the dipole–dipole coupling causing the relaxation process. For exponential correlation functions, the spectral density takes the Lorentzian form $J(\omega) = \frac{\tau_c}{1 + (\omega\tau_c)^2}$, where the parameter τ_c denotes a time constant (correlation time) describing the time scale of the motion while C^{HH} is referred to as a dipolar relaxation constant (it reflects the amplitude of the dipolar coupling). To reproduce relaxation data over a broad frequency range, one can use a sum of relaxation contributions, including Lorentzian spectral densities,^{15,17,27}

$$R_1^{HH}(\omega_H) = C_s^{HH} \left(\frac{\tau_s}{1 + \omega_H^2 \tau_s^2} + \frac{4\tau_s}{1 + 4\omega_H^2 \tau_s^2} \right) + C_i^{HH} \left(\frac{\tau_i}{1 + \omega_H^2 \tau_i^2} + \frac{4\tau_i}{1 + 4\omega_H^2 \tau_i^2} \right) + C_f^{HH} \left(\frac{\tau_f}{1 + \omega_H^2 \tau_f^2} + \frac{4\tau_f}{1 + 4\omega_H^2 \tau_f^2} \right) + A, \quad (3)$$

where τ_s , τ_i , and τ_f represent correlation times describing dynamical processes referred to as slow, intermediate, and fast ones, while C_s^{HH} , C_i^{HH} , and C_f^{HH} are the corresponding dipolar relaxation constants; and A is a frequency independent term that can represent a relaxation contribution associated with dynamical processes that are too

fast to lead to noticeable dependences on the resonance frequency in the covered frequency range.

The $R_1^{HN}(\omega_H)$ relaxation contribution leads to the Quadrupole Relaxation Enhancement (QRE) effects.^{27,49–52} The effect manifests itself as a frequency specific relaxation enhancement—an increase in the relaxation rate (often called “quadrupole peaks”). The origin of the can be (in a simplified way) explained as follows: The energy level structure of ^{14}N nuclei (spin 1) is affected

(even dominated in the considered frequency range) by quadrupole interactions. Consequently, there are magnetic fields at which the ^1H resonance frequency, ω_H , matches one of the transition frequencies of the ^{14}N nucleus between its energy levels. At those resonance frequencies, the ^1H magnetization is “taken over” by ^{14}N nuclei, which leads to a faster, more effective relaxation process. The $R_1^{HN}(\omega_H)$ relaxation contribution can be expressed as^{27,49}

$$R_1^{HN}(\omega_H) = C^{HN} \times \left[\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{1}{3} + \sin^2\Theta \cos^2\Phi \right) \left(\frac{\tau_C^{HN}}{1 + (\omega_H - \omega_-)^2 \tau_C^{HN2}} + \frac{\tau_C^{HN}}{1 + (\omega_H + \omega_-)^2 \tau_C^{HN2}} \right) \\ & + \left(\frac{1}{3} + \sin^2\Theta \sin^2\Phi \right) \left(\frac{\tau_C^{HN}}{1 + (\omega_H - \omega_+)^2 \tau_C^{HN2}} + \frac{\tau_C^{HN}}{1 + (\omega_H + \omega_+)^2 \tau_C^{HN2}} \right) \\ & + \left(\frac{1}{3} + \cos^2\Theta \right) \left(\frac{\tau_C^{HN}}{1 + (\omega_H - \omega_0)^2 \tau_C^{HN2}} + \frac{\tau_C^{HN}}{1 + (\omega_H + \omega_0)^2 \tau_C^{HN2}} \right) \end{aligned} \right], \quad (4)$$

where C^{HN} denotes the ^1H - ^{14}N dipolar relaxation constant. For a single ^1H - ^{14}N pair, it yields $C^{HN} = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{\gamma_H \gamma_N \hbar}{r_{HN}^3} \right)^2$ and includes the well-known physical constants (the vacuum permeability μ_0 , gyromagnetic ratios of proton γ_H and nitrogen γ_N , reduced Planck constant \hbar) and the ^1H - ^{14}N inter-spin distance, r_{HN} . The parameter τ_C^{HN} denotes the correlation time for the ^1H - ^{14}N dipole-dipole interactions; the angles Θ , Φ describe the orientation between the ^1H - ^{14}N dipole-dipole axis and the principal axis system of the electric field gradient at the position of ^{14}N (they are determined by the geometry of the molecule). The transition frequencies of ^{14}N are given as follows: $\omega_+ = a_Q(3 + \eta)$, $\omega_- = a_Q(3 - \eta)$, and $\omega_0 = 2a_Q\eta$, where the amplitude of the quadrupole coupling is equal to $a_Q = e^2 q Q / \hbar$, where Q denotes the quadrupolar moment of the nucleus, q is the zz component of the electric field gradient tensor, and η denotes the asymmetry parameter.

For hydrated biomolecular systems, there is a contribution to the relaxation process originating from water molecules. One should note at this stage that despite the heterogeneous structure of the systems, the relaxation process is single exponential, as pointed out in the next section. The presence of water also affects the dynamics of the macromolecular fraction, followed by the motion of the bound water fraction. For translation diffusion of water molecules in the vicinity of the macromolecular surface, the spectral density function, $J_{2D}^{trans}(\omega)$ (the index “2D” refers to two-dimensional diffusion) takes the form^{18,21,24,25}

$$J_{2D}^{trans}(\omega) = \tau_{trans} \ln \left[\frac{1 + (\omega \tau_{trans})^2}{\left(\frac{\tau_{trans}}{\tau_{res}} \right)^2 + (\omega \tau_{trans})^2} \right]. \quad (5)$$

The correlation time τ_{trans} is defined as $\tau_{trans} = \frac{d^2}{2D_{trans}}$, where D_{trans} denotes the diffusion coefficient, d is the diameter of the water molecule, and τ_{res} denotes the residence lifetime of water molecules

on the surface (the diffusion of water molecules near the protein surface is interrupted by forming temporary hydrogen bonds with the protein).

Further to that, correlation functions characterizing different kinds of molecular motion show at long times asymptotic behaviors that can be described as $C(t) \sim t^{-\alpha}$ ^{14,16} that leads to the asymptotic power law of the spectral density function $J(\omega) \sim \omega^{\alpha-1}$. Anticipating the outcome, the relaxation data for the hydrated systems can be reproduced in terms of the equation,

$$R_1(\omega_H) = C_{trans}^{HH} \tau_{trans} \left[\ln \left[\frac{1 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2}{\left(\frac{\tau_{trans}}{\tau_{res}} \right)^2 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2} \right] + 4 \ln \left[\frac{1 + (2\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2}{\left(\frac{\tau_{trans}}{\tau_{res}} \right)^2 + (2\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2} \right] \right] + B \omega_H^{-\beta}, \quad (6)$$

where C_{trans}^{HH} denotes the dipolar relaxation constant associated with the translation diffusion, while B denotes a pre-factor of the power law; and $\beta = 1 - \alpha$. As already pointed out in the introductory section, the power law dependence can be attributed to the dynamics of the protein backbones.^{33–39} The spin-lattice relaxation rates obtained for hydrated proteins are associated with ^1H water nuclei. The dynamics of protein backbones is probed indirectly as a result of cross-relaxation effects (transfer of magnetization) between ^1H nuclei of water and ^1H nuclei of the protein fraction caused by mutual dipole-dipole interactions.^{30,33–40}

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

^1H spin-lattice relaxation experiments have been performed in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 20 MHz at 298 K (room temperature) and 310 K (body temperature) using a “1 T NMR relaxometer,” produced by Stelar s.r.l. [Mede (PV), Italy]. The studies have been performed for collagen from bovine flexor tendon,

FIG. 1. ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for (a) artificial tissues at 298 K and 310 K and (b) collagen powder at 298 K and 310 K; solid lines represent the data for the tissues at 298 K (blue: tissue 1 and red: tissue 2) for comparison.

purchased as a lyophilized powder from Merck[®] Company and two kinds of commercially available collagen-based artificial tissues that are meant to serve multiple purposes (such as, for example, vaginal or pelvic organ prolapse). In addition to lyophilized collagen powder and the dry (non-hydrated) artificial tissues, hydrated forms of those materials have been prepared. Lyophilized collagen was stored for 48 h at a temperature of 298 K in a saturated water vapor atmosphere. After 48 h, the hydration level was $\sim 28\%$ (water weight content in the sample). The same hydration procedure was applied to the artificial tissue samples. The tissue samples were stored at room temperature (298 K) for 18 h under a saturated water vapor atmosphere. After 18 h, tissue 1 reached 26% and tissue 2 reached 34 wt. % of water. During the measurements, the sample temperature was set using a built-in variable temperature controller with an accuracy of 1 K. The switching time of the magnet was set to 3 ms. The decaying and saturating magnetization curves obtained with pre-polarized (PP/S) and non-pre-polarized (NP/S) sequences, respectively, were recorded for logarithmically distributed time values, including 32 points. The relaxation processes show mono-exponential behavior for all measurements in the whole frequency range. Examples of the magnetization curves (^1H magnetization vs time) are shown in the Appendix (Figs. 6–11).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis

^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for two kinds of collagen-based artificial tissues in the solid (non-hydrated) form are shown in Fig. 1(a). The first observation that can be made is that the data for both kinds of tissue (almost) overlap, and they are, in fact, not affected by the temperature. It is only natural to compare the data obtained for collagen powder [Fig. 1(b)]. The comparison clearly shows that there is no significant difference between the relaxation features of the tissues and collagen powder. The data shown in Fig. 1 have been analyzed in terms of Eqs. (2) and (3). The position of the QRE peaks is determined by the quadrupole coupling, a_Q , and the asymmetry parameter, η . Consequently, the parameters were calculated from the position of the peaks. Following this line—the relative amplitudes of the quadrupole peaks depend on the angles Θ and Φ and their correlation time, τ_Q . These parameters were determined from the shape of the peaks and only slightly adjusted in the fits.

Figure 2(a) shows the outcome of the analysis for tissue 1 at 298 K, while in Fig. 2(b), the analogous analysis for solid collagen at 298 K is shown. The obtained parameters are collected in Table I. They are obviously very similar.

FIG. 2. ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for (a) artificial tissues at 298 K and (b) collagen powder at 298 K, analyzed in terms of Eqs. (2) and (3). $R_{1,s}$: dashed line, $R_{1,i}$: dotted-dashed line, $R_{1,f}$: dotted-dashed-dotted line, A : dotted line, R_1^{HN} : solid line, and R_1 : solid black line.

TABLE I. Parameters obtained from the analysis of ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for artificial tissues and collagen in terms of Eqs. (2) and (3). If some of the relaxation data overlap (in a very good approximation), in parentheses, the additional datasets to which the set of parameters applies are indicated.

$C_s \times 10^6$ (Hz^2)	$\tau_s \times 10^{-6}$ (s)	$C_i \times 10^7$ (Hz^2)	$\tau_i \times 10^{-7}$ (s)	$C_f \times 10^8$ (Hz^2)	$\tau_f \times 10^{-8}$ (s)	$C^{HN} \times 10^7$ (Hz^2)	$\tau_Q \times 10^{-6}$ (s)	a_Q (MHz)	η	Θ (deg)	Φ (deg)	A (s^{-1})
Artificial tissue 1, solid, 298 K (tissue 1, 310 K; tissue 2, 298 K, 310 K)												
53.3 ± 1.1	3.35 ± 0.1	26.0 ± 0.9	2.8 ± 0.07	6.5 ± 0.7	2.2 ± 0.2	11.1 ± 1.3	1.1 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 0.02	54.8 ± 5.3	46.6 ± 5.4	8.4 ± 2.4
Collagen, solid, 298 K, 310 K												
57.2 ± 0.9	5.0 ± 0.2	21.9 ± 0.7	3.4 ± 0.08	7.5 ± 0.6	2.7 ± 0.2	10.1 ± 1.1	1.5 ± 0.2	3.34 ± 0.02	0.4 ± 0.01	53.4 ± 4.9	49.5 ± 5.8	13.8 ± 2.5
Artificial tissue 1, hydrated, 298 K												
5.7 ± 0.2	5.2 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.3	2.2 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.009	0.4 ± 0.007	59.5 ± 3.9	49.2 ± 2.6	10.3 ± 0.8
Artificial tissue 1, hydrated, 310 K												
7.6 ± 0.2	4.9 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.3	2.7 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.3	1.9 ± 0.3	1.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.007	0.4 ± 0.006	75.0 ± 7.6	48.7 ± 2.0	8.0 ± 1.0
Artificial tissue 2, hydrated, 298 K (310 K)												
7.0 ± 0.1	4.4 ± 0.08	3.4 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.006	0.4 ± 0.005	70.0 ± 4.3	51.7 ± 1.7	8.5 ± 0.7
Collagen, hydrated, 298 K (310 K)												
5.9 ± 0.05	7.6 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.1	3.6 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.1	1.15 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.01	0.4 ± 0.007	55.3 ± 3.4	49.1 ± 2.5	6.8 ± 0.6

FIG. 3. ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for (a) hydrated artificial tissues at 298 K and 310 K and (b) hydrated collagen at 298 K and 310 K; solid lines represent the data for the hydrated tissues at 298 K (blue: tissue 1 and red: tissue 2) for comparison.

With this knowledge, we have turned our attention to the hydrated artificial tissues in comparison with collagen. After 18 h, tissue 1 reaches 26 wt.% of water, while in tissue 2, the water content is higher, 34%, after the same time. In comparison, for collagen powder, 48 h are required to reach 28 wt.% of water. Figure 3(a) shows the ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for the hydrated artificial tissues. The relaxation features and, hence, the dynamics of the hydrated tissues are considerably different than their solid counterparts. For tissue 1, the temperature effect is small but visible, while for tissue 2, there is almost no temperature effect

observed. In Fig. 3(b), the relaxation data for hydrated collagen are shown and compared with those for the tissues. The temperature effect for collagen is also negligible, but the results for hydrated collagen and the hydrated tissues differ considerably. It is important to stress that despite hydration, the QRE effects remain well-pronounced.

The data for the hydrated tissues have been analyzed in the first step, following the strategy for the solid systems. The obtained parameters are included in Table I, while Fig. 4 shows the decomposition of the overall relaxation rates into individual contributions.

FIG. 4. ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for hydrated artificial tissues and hydrated collagen powder analyzed in terms of Eqs. (2) and (3). $R_{1,s}$: dashed line, $R_{1,j}$: dotted-dashed line, $R_{1,f}$: dotted-dashed-dotted line, A : dotted line, R_1^{HN} : solid line, and R_1 : solid black line.

TABLE II. Parameters obtained from the analysis of ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for hydrated artificial tissues and collagen in terms of Eq. (6). The translation diffusion coefficient has been calculated from the relationship $D_{\text{trans}} = \frac{d^2}{2\tau_{\text{trans}}}$, $d = 2.8 \text{ \AA}$. The units of the parameter B depend on the value of β : $\text{Hz}^{(\beta+1)}$.

B	β	$C_{\text{trans}}^{\text{HH}}$ (Hz^2)	τ_{trans} (s)	D_{trans} (m^2/s)
Artificial tissue 1, hydrated, 298 K				
5720 ± 298	0.38 ± 0.007	$(8.7 \pm 1.5) \times 10^7$	$(7.6 \pm 1.0) \times 10^{-9}$	5.2×10^{-12}
Artificial tissue 1, hydrated, 310 K				
$10\,430 \pm 520$	0.43 ± 0.009	$(8.7 \pm 1.7) \times 10^7$	$(3.5 \pm 0.9) \times 10^{-9}$	1.1×10^{-11}
Artificial tissue 2, hydrated, 298 K (310 K)				
7260 ± 240	0.40 ± 0.003	$(8.0 \pm 3.1) \times 10^7$	$(1.8 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-9}$	2.2×10^{-11}
Collagen, hydrated, 298 K (310 K)				
$(79 \pm 13) \times 10^4$	0.94 ± 0.02	$(3.4 \pm 0.3) \times 10^8$	$(1.6 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-9}$	2.5×10^{-11}

Although this approach enables a quantitative comparison of the dynamical properties of the solid and hydrated systems, to get insight into the mechanism of motion in the hydrated systems, Eq. (6) has been applied. Before doing that, the calculated R_1^{HN} (obtained from the fits shown in Fig. 4) relaxation contribution has been subtracted from the experimental data. The outcome of this approach is summarized in Table II, while Fig. 5 shows the analysis. Looking at the parameters collected in Table II, one sees that the values of the β parameter for hydrated collagen and the hydrated

artificial tissues considerably differ. This effect and several others are discussed in the next section.

B. Discussion

As already pointed out, the relaxation properties (and, hence, the dynamics) of non-hydrated collagen and non-hydrated artificial tissues are very similar. To get a quantitative insight into the dynamical properties of the solid materials, the data have been decomposed

FIG. 5. ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for hydrated artificial tissues and hydrated collagen powder analyzed in terms of Eq. (6). 2D translation diffusion: dotted-dashed line, power law contribution: dashed line, and R_1 : solid black line.

into three relaxation contributions expressed in terms of Lorentzian spectral densities attributed to dynamical processes referred to as slow, intermediate, and fast ones. The obtained correlation times are of the order of 10^{-6} , 10^{-7} , and 10^{-8} s, respectively. The correlation times as well as the other quantities—the corresponding dipolar relaxation constants and the parameters related to the ^1H - ^{14}N relaxation contribution (C^{HN} , τ_Q , a_Q , η , Θ , and Φ)—are closely related to those obtained for other kinds of solid proteins,²⁷ contributing to the observation that the relaxation features of solid proteins follow a universal pattern. The pattern is only very weakly affected by temperature (in the investigated temperature range).

Treating this quantitative characterization as a reference, an analogous analysis has been performed for hydrated collagen and the hydration of artificial tissues. At this stage, it is worth pointing out that the hydration process for collagen is slower than for the tissues. The comparable hydration levels (28% for collagen, 26% for tissue, and 34% for tissue 2) have been reached after 48 h for collagen and 18 h for tissues. As far as collagen is concerned, the changes in the relaxation rates for the hydrated collagen compared to the non-hydrated one are mainly reflected by a considerably smaller value of the dipolar relaxation constants, C_s and C_i , associated with the dynamical process occurring on the slow and intermediate time scales, respectively. The two dipolar relaxation constants are reduced by about one order of magnitude upon hydration. The C_f value for hydrated collagen is lower by about five compared to that for the non-hydrated one. The dipolar relaxation constant describing the ^1H - ^{14}N dipole-dipole interactions is about one order of magnitude smaller for the hydrated systems compared to the non-hydrated ones. This implies a lower amplitude of the quadrupole peaks. One can expect that in the presence of water, the internal dynamics of the protein backbones become faster, leading to a partial averaging of the amplitude of the ^1H - ^{14}N dipole-dipole coupling. The correlation times are affected by hydration to a much lesser extent. This finding can be explained (to some extent) by cross-relaxation effects between pools of hydrogen atoms of different mobility.^{30–32} The relaxation data for hydrated collagen and the hydrated artificial tissues differ, as shown in Fig. 3(b). Nevertheless, comparing the parameters for the non-hydrated and hydrated tissues, one again observes that hydration leads to a reduction of the dipolar relaxation constants, no considerably affecting the correlation times. The reduction of the dipolar relaxation constants is by factors of about eight, six, and three for C_s , C_i , and C_f , respectively. The ^1H - ^{14}N dipolar relaxation constant, C^{HN} , is also lower by about factor ten for the hydrated tissues compared to the non-hydrated ones. Although the temperature effect is more significant for tissue 1 compared to tissue 2, it is small anyway (similarly to hydrated collagen).

At this stage, one should point out that for complex molecular systems, the decomposition into relaxation contributions mimics (to some extent) a distribution of correlation times. When the overall relaxation rates stem from many dynamical processes involving different mechanisms and pools of hydrogen atoms, this kind of parametrization is very useful. However, to get a deeper insight into the mechanism of motion in the hydrated systems, the concept [represented by Eq. (6)] of two-dimensional (surface) diffusion of water molecules and a power law relaxation contribution has been exploited and verified against the experimental data. It has turned out that this approach allows for the successful reproduction of the

data, confirming the assumed mechanism of motion. The obtained translation diffusion coefficients (in the vicinity of the macromolecular surfaces) for hydrated collagen and hydrated tissue 2 are by two orders of magnitude lower compared to the water diffusion coefficient in bulk (about 2×10^{-9} m²/s at 298 K). For tissue 1, the slowing down of the diffusion process is even more significant (about factor 400). It is of interest to compare the dipolar relaxation constants associated with the water diffusion, $C_{\text{trans}}^{\text{HH}}$. For hydrated collagen, this quantity is by a factor of about four larger compared to that for the artificial tissues. This might be explained by a different arrangement of water molecules in the vicinity of collagen chains in pure collagen and in the biomaterials, or/and a higher population of the pool of water molecules undergoing surface diffusion in the case of collagen. As far as the macromolecular dynamics are concerned, the β parameter for the hydrated tissues is about 0.4, which is relatively close to the value theoretically predicted for polymer reptation dynamics: 0.5.^{14,16} The power law for the tissues is much different from that for hydrated collagen, $\beta = 0.94$ (close to 1), and different from the typical values reported for proteins (0.5–0.8).^{39–41} This shows that the dynamics of the macromolecular fraction in the hydrated biomaterials are considerably different than in the hydrated collagen.

V. CONCLUSION

^1H spin-lattice relaxation experiments performed for solid (non-hydrated) collagen and two kinds of artificial tissues have revealed very similar relaxation (and, hence, dynamical) features. The decomposition of the relaxation data into contributions expressed in terms of Lorentzian spectral densities has led to a series of parameters that have been used for the purpose of comparison with the outcome of analogous analysis for hydrated materials (collagen and artificial tissues). It has turned out that hydration leads to a reduction of dipolar relaxation constants, while the correlation times are not considerably affected by the hydration process. Water molecules in the hydrated systems undergo translation diffusion in the vicinity of the macromolecular surfaces (two-dimensional translation diffusion)—the motion is two orders of magnitude lower compared to water diffusion in bulk. The motion of the macromolecular fraction (collagen) in the hydrated tissues is characterized by a power law of about 0.4, while for hydrated collagen, the power law is close to 1 (0.94).

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Elzbieta Masiewicz: Investigation (lead); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Farman Ullah:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal). **Adrianna Mieloch:** Investigation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Janusz Godlewski:**

Methodology (equal); Resources (equal). **Danuta Kruk**: Conceptualization (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Supervision (lead); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (lead).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10798400>.

FIG. 6. Magnetization curves for solid (non-hydrated) artificial tissue 1 at (a) 298 K and (b) 310 K. Solid lines represent single-exponential fits.

FIG. 7. Magnetization curves for solid (non-hydrated) artificial tissue 2 at (a) 298 K and (b) 310 K. Solid lines represent single-exponential fits.

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FIG. 8. Magnetization curves for solid (non-hydrated) collagen at (a) 298 K and (b) 310 K. Solid lines represent single-exponential fits.

FIG. 9. Magnetization curves for hydrated artificial tissue 1 at (a) 298 K and (b) 310 K. Solid lines represent single-exponential fits.

FIG. 10. Magnetization curves for hydrated artificial tissue 2 at (a) 298 K and (b) 310 K. Solid lines represent single-exponential fits.

FIG. 11. Magnetization curves for hydrated collagen at (a) 298 K and (b) 310 K. Solid lines represent single-exponential fits.

APPENDIX: EXAMPLES OF ^1H MAGNETIZATION CURVES FOR ARTIFICIAL TISSUES AND COLLAGEN SYSTEMS

Figures 6–11 show time evolution of ^1H magnetization for non-hydrated artificial tissues (Figs. 6 and 7), non-hydrated collagen (Fig. 8), hydrated artificial tissues (Figs. 9 and 10) and hydrated

collagen (Fig. 11) at selected resonance frequencies. The data have been fitted in terms of a single exponential function.

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